

STADIO School of Education
BEd Hons Inclusive Education

Title of Study:

Improving Lesson Planning for Teachers with ADHD: A Study of Artificial Intelligence's Influence on Time Management and Inclusivity

Jeanne van Heerden

Supervisor-Dr JP Grundling

DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

I, Jeanne van Heerden, declare that:

“Improving Lesson Planning for Teachers with ADHD: A Study of Artificial Intelligence’s Influence on Time Management and Inclusivity”, is my own unaided work, both in content and execution. All the resources I used for this research are cited and referred to in the reference list by means of a comprehensive referencing system. Apart from the normal guidance from my supervisor, I have received no assistance except as stated in the acknowledgements. I declare that the content of this proposal/research report has never been used for any qualification at any tertiary institution.

I further declare that I have read the STADIO Plagiarism Policy and am fully informed of the expectations of academic integrity placed on me as a student of this institution.

Signature

20/06/2025

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ABSTRACT

Educators with Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), who are simultaneously balancing caregiving responsibilities, frequently encounter challenges with time management, planning and staying organized. This qualitative self-study considers how the incorporation of artificial intelligence applications like Magic School AI into lesson planning, can be support and alleviate these burdens to create an effective and inclusive classroom environment for both students and teachers. This research is outlined by the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles and shaped with the researcher's personal experience. Magic School AI is an application that acts as an education assistant, prompt inputs for instruction are used to create assessments, classroom resources directly aligned to the curriculum standards and differentiated lesson plans. Findings are suggested from data collected from a peer interview, several classroom observations across year groups and reflective journaling over a 10-week period. The results suggest that Magic School AI, reduces administrative burdens, enhances time management, and supports inclusive pedagogies. However, several ethical limitations were observed, the risk of overreliance on artificial intelligence as well as the generation of content that may be illegitimate, irrelevant, misaligned and culturally insensitive. Additionally, the researcher contributed to the implementing and development of a school-wide AI policy. The researcher took part in the Middle States Responsible AI Leaders (RAIL) endorsement, relating understandings from the study in practice. These findings highlight the need for further study into how AI tools can effectively support neurodiverse educators within the inclusive educational system. This study highlights the potential and risks of integrating AI applications to support neurodiverse educators, pointing out the importance of considerate implementation and ongoing research in inclusive educational practices.

KEYWORDS: *Artificial intelligence; Magic School AI; Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD); Educators with ADHD; Artificial Intelligence in Education; Lesson Planning; Time Management; Inclusive Education; Universal Design for Learning (UDL); Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK); Neurodiversity; Educational Technology; AI Ethics in Education; AI Policy in Schools; Reflective Practice*

HOW EACH CHAPTER CONTRIBUTES TO THE OVERALL STUDY:

An introduction sets the context in each chapter, followed by a literature review that frames the research inquiry. Scholarly rigour is demonstrated in the methodology section, while data evidence is presented by the findings. The insights are translated into practical insights by the conclusion. The

chapters all tell a convincing narrative of how Magic School AI can aid teachers with ADHD by improving lesson planning and developing a richer inclusivity and engagement in their learning environments.

CLARIFICATION OF KEY CONCEPTS

Inclusive Education: An approach that aims to address the diverse needs of all students.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): Technology that simulates human intelligence processes to assist in various tasks.

Magic School AI: A specific AI tool designed to assist educators create lesson plans and assessments.

Student Engagement: The level of interest, motivation, and participation that students exhibit in their learning activities.

Teaching Efficiency: The ability of educators to deliver effective instruction while managing their time and resources effectively.

ADHD (Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder): ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by difficulties with attention regulation, impulsivity, and hyperactivity.

Primary Years Program (PYP): The Primary Years Program (PYP) is an educational framework designed for students aged 3 to 12 years that emphasizes inquiry-based learning and holistic development.

Personalized Learning: Personalized learning refers to educational approaches that tailor instruction to meet individual students' needs, preferences, and interests.

Reflective Practice: Reflective practice involves critically analysing one's teaching experiences to improve future performance.

CHAPTER 1:

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The landscape of education has been reshaped by the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) across diverse contexts. Educators are faced with both extraordinary possibilities and many challenges as schools handle the rapid advancements in AI technologies (Holmes et al., 2019). Despite the growing presence of these technologies, there remains a lack of practical guidance to effectively implementing AI tools in the classroom and in policies, particularly for teachers navigating neurodiversity's (Barkley, 2015). Educators managing ADHD, often face unique hurdles when it comes to time management, planning and simultaneously having care giving responsibilities (Barkley, 2015).

The report explores Magic School AI - a collection of AI - powered tools tailored purposely to support lesson planning, administrative tasks and instructional differentiation. The study is grounded in the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) model and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) philosophies (Mishra & Koehler, 2006; CAST, 2018), it assumes a qualitative self-study methodology that includes introspective journaling, classroom observations, and peer reviews. Ethical implications, particularly those of wider implications of AI use in educational settings, responsible data handling, participant anonymity were fundamental to the research design (Williamson & Eynon, 2020; U.S. Department of Education, 2023).

While AI's potential to enhance productivity and engagements has been widely acknowledged (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; World Economic Forum, 2024), there is limited research examining its role in supporting the well-being and pedagogical practices for neurodiverse teachers (Kouroupa, Mavropoulou, & Lemonidis, 2024). The study aims to address a critical gap in the literature by centring the lived experiences of an ICT Primary Years Program (PYP) teacher with ADHD and caregiving responsibilities, suggesting insights into how Magic School AI integration might support inclusive education, improve teaching practices and a better work-life balance.

The findings offer insights into the possibilities and limitations of integrating Magic School AI into the modern classroom setting. By informing future applications of AI in diverse educational settings and looking deeply into how AI technology can be applied to support both educator wellbeing and student engagement authentically. Furthermore, investigating how AI might serve as both a support system

and challenge, raising questions of ethical use and overreliance and authenticity (Holmes et al., 2019; TeachAI, 2024).

1.2 BACKGROUND TO STUDY:

Artificial Intelligence has become unquestionably immersive in recent years and has brought a noticeable change in reshaping educational practices and expectations (Holmes et al., 2019; Luckin et al., 2016; U.S. Department of Education, 2023). It can be said that its presence is now undeniable. But despite its rapid onset and influence, it remains that few have been given the right guidance or tools to be able to use it effectively, or guard against its dangers (World Economic Forum, 2024; TeachAI, 2024). Questions such as ‘How do we use it?’ and ‘How do we go about incorporating it into our policies and frameworks?’ have dominated academic discourse (U.S. Department of Education, 2023; Williamson & Eynon, 2020).

Policy which is robust and a sense of leadership in the new age is idly recognized. Recommendations include AI task forces which promote AI literacy, and who established user guidelines and provide professional development (World Economic Forum, 2024; TeachAI, 2024). In this rise of the AI age, education leaders are urged to see that the Artificial wave of help supports and augments human interaction, aligning with its ethical standards and educational goals rather than replacing it (U.S. Department of Education, 2023; World Economic Forum, 2025). Participating as AI Committee lead developer at school, I have been responsible part of a team developing the school’s first AI Policy for and participating in the Responsible AI Leaders (RAIL) course, furthering our commitment to responsible and ethical AI practices. This experience has provided practical and theoretical context and directly informed this study.

How AI applications, particularly Magic School AI, can support and help teachers stay organized - particularly those diagnosed with Attention Deficit/ Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) or facing significant family stresses is the specific highlight of this study. There is good research to back the claim that teachers who suffer from ADHD or family stresses struggle to adopt an inclusive learning environment (Barkley, 2015; DuPaul & Weyandt, 2006). AI Tools like Magic School AI is designed specifically to streamline administrative tasks, support individualized lesson planning, and help with interventions such as behavioural support, thereby giving the teacher time to focus on more meaningful interactions with their students (Holmes et al., 2019; Luckin et al., 2016). The implementation of AI - generated lesson plans which are tailored to the individual saves time and contributes to a better and healthier

work life balance and personal satisfaction (U.S. Department of Education, 2023; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

Students with various special needs have also been given a boost but certain AI technologies in the recent past and the literature on the subject underscores the potential of the AI (Holmes et al., 2019; World Economic Forum, 2025). However, certain barriers like equitable access, ethical implementation and ongoing support for educators are essential to see this benefit realized (Williamson & Eynon, 2020; U.S. Department of Education, 2023). By focusing on the lived experiences of a teacher using Magic School AI - especially one who manages a busy family life and lives with the challenges posed by an ADHD diagnoses this study aims to highlights the practical insights and recommendations for integrating AI in schools responsibly.

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT:

Teachers who struggle or suffer from ADHD find it hard to stay organized and make proper use of their time, this impacts their ability to foster learning spaces which are conducive to inclusive learning. AI is known to be very useful in terms of enhancing productivity, efficiency and engagement but there is a lack of research to support its role in supporting teachers with ADHD. This study seeks to change that view and shed light on the way in which Magic School AI can help teachers create individualized Learning Plans (IEPs), lesson planning and administrative tasks. In this way allowing the teachers to focus their energy on engaging their students as well as their time with their family.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

The following research questions guided the study:

1.4.1 The principal research question

How does the integration of Magic School AI influence the teaching practices, time management, and perceptions of inclusivity of a teacher with ADHD and family responsibilities?

1.4.2 The secondary research questions

- How does the use of Magic School AI change the teacher's approach to lesson planning and classroom organization?

- What is the teacher's experience of the impact of Magic School AI on their time management, family responsibilities and workload?
- In what ways, if any, does the teacher perceive that Magic School AI supports or hinders inclusive teaching practices?
- What are the teacher's observations of the effects of Magic School AI-assisted lessons on student engagement?
- From a teacher's perspective, what are the benefits and challenges of using Magic School AI?

1.5 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

AIMS:

The study intended to report on a teacher who manages ADHD and family responsibilities, and how their use of Magic School impacts their classroom practices, teacher involvement and student engagement.

OBJECTIVES:

Each research objective in this study is closely aligned with specific secondary questions to ensure a focused and coherent investigation.

The secondary question in this study aligns with the objectives of the research to guarantee a focused and sensible study. The objective to observe changes in the student's engagement prior and after using AI - assisted lessons aligns with the question "What are the teacher's observations of the effects of Magic School AI-assisted lessons on student engagement?" The objective to evaluate the time saved in lesson planning using Magic School AI is covered by both "How does the use of Magic School AI change the teacher's approach to lesson planning and classroom organization?" and "What is the teacher's experience of the impact of Magic School AI on their time management, family responsibilities and workload?"

The objective to take note of individual reflections on using AI as a teacher with ADHD is linked to the question, "What are the perceived benefits and challenges of using Magic School AI from the teacher's perspective?" The objective to gauge how technologies like Magic School AI helped

inclusive teaching practices by supporting diverse learners' needs is aligned with "In what ways, if any, does the teacher perceive that Magic School AI supports or hinders inclusive teaching practices?"

Lastly, the objective to look at barriers faced by teachers when weaving Magic School AI into their classrooms is also addressed by the question on perceived benefits and challenges.

RATIONALE AND SIGNIFICANCE:

This study was particularly compelling as it illuminated a notable gap in existing research regarding teachers with ADHD who have family and professional responsibilities and their engagement with AI. By analysing the fields like the engagement of students and organizing and teaching skills, this research broke substantial ground on how the use of Magic School AI had the potential to enhance inclusivity and work life balance for educators.

1.6 CONCLUSION:

This chapter provided a bird's eye view of the study's problem statement, research questions, aims, objectives, background, and educational significance. It served as a foundation behind why Magic School AI may transform teaching practices for educators with ADHD.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

CHAPTER OUTLINE

This chapter reviews and looks at the literature which exists relevant to the use and integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education. It focused on its implications for teaching, which is deemed to be inclusive, the support of teachers (especially those which suffer from ADHD) and student engagement. The review addresses key concepts and definitions, theoretical frameworks which underlie AI in education, findings from previous studies, and makes note of the gaps which this research seeks to address.

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The rise of AI has changed various sectors of the economy, with education being a sizable area of impact (Luckin et al., 2016). As tools in the Artificial Intelligence field become more powerful, questions have arisen regarding their effective integration, whether their use is ethical, and their potential to support both teachers and students particularly in inclusive settings. This literature review seeks to give a comprehensive analysis of the current research on AI in education, highlighting its role in supporting teachers with ADHD and enhancing student engagement. Furthermore, this review will consolidate findings from existing research, gauging them through established theoretical frameworks and identifying contextual gaps and disparities.

The reflective journal entries of the researcher highlights the above-mentioned challenges. For example, on February 4th, Magic School AI's Schedule Builder was used to structure the researchers and their toddler's day, which assisted in managing decision-making overwhelm, substantiating that administrative and organising support lowers anxiety (Reflection Journal, Feb 4, 2025).

This aligns with the idea that AI tools offer scaffolding that aid and benefit neurodiverse educators (Almalki and Alharbi, 2021).

2.2 KEY CONCEPTS AND DEFINITIONS

Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIEd): AIEd refers to the incorporation of AI systems and technology which can aid teaching and learning, in addition to natural language learning. These include machine learning and are usually adaptive in nature. (Holmes et al., 2019).

Inclusive Education: Inclusive education knocks down barriers to participation and success and aims to address the diverse needs of all learners. (UNESCO, 2017)

Teacher Neurodiversity (ADHD): Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a mental condition that can seriously harm the individual's ability to organize, manage their time properly and execute various functions in their daily professional and personal lives (Barkley, 2015). More recent studies revealed that teachers, and other professionals with ADHD may encounter specific and meaningful challenges in managing classroom and administrative tasks (Hotte-Meunier et al.).

Magic School AI: Magic School AI is a platform offering AI-powered tools designed to support educators by reducing the cognitive overload and support inclusive instruction practices in the classroom by, suggesting behaviour interventions, providing feedback and suggestions, and generating lesson plans (Magic School AI, 2024a; 2024b).

Further context for how these AI tools is experienced in real classroom settings, was incorporation by looking into peer interview data. Peer educators using Magic School AI assisted in illustrating the practical advantages and challenges beyond theoretical descriptions.

In my reflection journal, the use of Magic School's Class Newsletter Tool (Jan 20, Feb 5, and Feb 17) notably saved time and mental effort in composing school-parent communication, allowing me to shift attention to parenting responsibilities.

These understandings resonate with the time-saving potential discussed by West Vancouver Schools (2023), where educators used comparable tools for better efficiency, productivity and better family balance.

2.3 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

2.3.1 Universal Design for Learning (UDL)

The Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework lobbies for learning environments which are flexible, and which makes space for individual differences in learning. It gives educators a theoretical background for inclusive learning (CAST, 2018). Recent studies (Choi, 2024) have shown they can personalise instruction and support learners who have various diverse needs, when AI tools have been aligned with UDL principles. In other words, the inclusive student-centred classroom is swifter and more inclusive with technology is integrated with AI

One that's highly adaptable and serves a wider variety of learners with different needs and abilities in a fraction of the time. This reduces the overwhelming cognitive overload by offering immediate adjustments to teacher's lesson plans to improve productivity in the classroom (Flavian, 2016; Bradari et al., 2025). This is useful not only to support neurodiverse educators but also the fluctuating teaching environments. The commitment to minimise barriers in educational settings emphasizes the significance of the UDL in this context. AI Applications like Magic School AI are specifically created to support immediate scaffolding, multi-sensory instruction, and differentiated instruction suggestions, all of which embody UDL principles (Magic School, 2024; Rose & Meyer, 2002). These claims were

validated by a peer interview highlighting how Magic School AI's scaffolding tools recommendations align closely with UDL's adaptable and inclusive instruction ethos, catering to the diverse needs of student while organizing their own mental load.

The researcher logged consistent use of Magic School AI for lesson planning (Jan 15, 28), feedback drafting (Jan 9, Feb 11), and rubric creation (Jan 13, Feb 13) over a 10-week term. Although some tools like the Rubric Generator occasionally needed amendments, as seen in several entries, they provided initial starting points.

This reiterates the awareness that AI tools rarely offer perfect results, and need fine tuning, but these applications serve as support systems to assist overstretched teachers (Alharbi and Almalki, 2021).

2.3.2 Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK)

As recent studies have heightened the need for TPACK to add immersive technologies like AI, for teachers to adapt their expertise with the help from technology to use these tools in a diverse classroom setting (Voogt et al.; Koh, Chai, and Wong). The TPACK framework observes the interconnectedness of technology, teacher knowledge, and content proficiency. Tools such as Magic School AI offer support to teachers by generating custom differentiated content. Adapting this framework to the research questions permits an in-depth examination of how educators with ADHD relate and interact with AI tools, content, and pedagogy in their instructional practices (Mishra and Koehler, 2006). The Peer teacher interview data backs this interconnectedness, revealing that teachers with neurodiversity find Magic School AI beneficial for making connections between technological facilitation and content delivery, thereby enhancing instructive methods fitted to their needs.

2.4 REVIEW OF PREVIOUS RESEARCH

2.4.1 AI Integration in Education

Recent studies have shown that AI technology can enhance the doing of administrative tasks, personalize learning and provide insights backed by data to help instructional decision making (Holmes et al., 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Applications like Magic School AI can assist with lesson plans, scaffold, differentiate, and intervene in behaviour using certain tools, all of which support teachers in managing complex classroom situations and environments. This aids to reduce cognitive overwhelm, especially teacher with neurodiverse needs, to deliver qualitative and engaging lessons for students by focusing more on their instruction (Angelone and Burton, 2024). Due to limited training,

lack of institutional support and uncertainty about ethical implications, many educators are still hesitant about integrating AI to improve lesson delivery (Wang et al. 2021)

Magic School AI significantly improve elementary student academic results and assisted teachers in delivering adaptive yet structured lessons (Khan, Tabassum, and Umar, 2024). This supports wider findings that AI could reduce the teacher's workload whilst enriching personalization.

Findings from the peer interview align with these results, indicating that even a single use has the potential to significantly reduce administrative burden and increased confidence in lesson delivery by using Magic School AI, underlining its potential practical influence.

2.4.2 AI and Inclusive Teaching

AI can potentially be very useful in promoting inclusivity by moulding and changing content to meet the needs of diverse learners, including those with learning disabilities or language impairments as well as enabling teachers—especially those with cognitive disparities like ADHD (Chalkiadakis et al. 2024). Most research focus on student benefit of AI, it is proven that AI lessen the burden of administrative tasks for teachers, by providing real time instructional support and personalizing lesson plans (Kumar et al. 2021; Feng et al. 2021). These are life changing tools for teachers with ADHD, who suddenly have the needed assistance with organization, planning, and task implementation, assisting with capacities that are challenging (Vogt and Kuhn, 2023). Magic School AI demonstrates practical value to inclusive educational teachings by showing its capacity to generate modifications to ideas, adjust language levels, and manage behavioural interventions (Magic School AI, 2024a; 2024b).

Improvements in focus, time management and a reduction in anxiety were noted in AI based technology, designed to assist teachers with differently abled needs (Almalki and Alharbi, 2021). Adequate teacher training, ethical oversight and fair policy frameworks is required, according to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), meaningful use of AI in teaching depends on trusted teaching staff qualified to leverage AI tools properly to enhance learning (OECD 2023). Similarly, The European Commissions Digital Education Plan of 2024 stresses that it is of utmost importance that diverse data is used to ensure fairness in AI systems. This reduces bias, and strengths the need to reinforce human-centred and ethical implementation of AI in education (European Commission, 2024). Interviews revealed that, while Magic School AI offers useful modifications and differentiation, human oversight is critical. This ensures alignment with inclusive teaching goals and reflects the concerns found in the literature about ethical AI use and human oversight (Almalki & Alharbi, 2021; Chalkiadakis et al., 2024).

The researcher's reflection journal confirmed that AI tools like the Choice Board Generator (Feb 10) supported UDL principles by recommending differentiated task ideas, improving student engagement, and decreasing the planning stress. Mirroring that a successful TPACK incorporation requires reflective practice, particularly in inclusive settings (Chai et al, 2013).

2.4.3 Teacher Support and ADHD

There is limited research stating the case for AI tools and their use by teachers with ADHD. The research that is available indicates that teachers struggling with ADHD also struggle with tasks including time management, organization, and the balance between their personal and professional lives. (Barkley, 2015; DuPaul & Weyandt, 2006). Early indicators in the existing literature does move toward a case where AI can alleviate some of the routine tasks by automating them (Holmes et al., 2019). However, the empirical researched evidence specifically focusing on teachers with ADHD remains scarce in this area, noting the opportunity for further study. Case studies revealed various accounts of teachers using these tools to simplify tasks, manage workload, and enhance instructional confidence. Though not peer-reviewed, these case studies present valuable practitioner insights that highlight the application's relevance to the neurodiverse teacher's experience (Magic School AI, 2024a; 2024b). This adds to this emerging evidence by affording qualitative data on how a teacher with ADHD could experiences Magic School AI's support.

2.4.4 AI and Student Engagement

Studies have indicated that instruction assisted by AI can help with student engagements, especially in inquiry-based learning classrooms such as those in the Primary Years Program (PYP) (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019). Technologies which are interactive differentiate instruction and give real time feedback, leading to higher levels of participation and motivation. Magic School AI's student engagement planning and feedback generator tools have shown to contributed positively to student attentiveness and motivation and are validated by peer feedback (Khan et al, 2024).

2.5 SYNTHESIS AND ANALYSIS

While the literature is welcome to the promise of AI, several issues still exist which are problematic. Robust teacher training, ethical questions regarding privacy and the thought of widening the educational gap in terms of access to AI tools are all problems which need to be addressed (Williamson and Eynon 2020; OECD 2023). The point where inclusive teaching, teacher neurodiversity and AI meet is underexplored, especially in terms of the practical things you can use in supporting

teachers with ADHD. The gap that was noticed is how AI can sensibly be supportive to neurodiverse teachers, including teachers with ADHD. Standing studies reveal time management, organization, and other workload challenges commonly faced by teachers with ADHD, but very little empirical data is available on how AI tools might alleviate these challenges (Almalki and Alharbi 2021).

This study aligns Magic School AI to UDL and TPACK frameworks within a neurodiverse context. Case studies, peer interviews and scholarly sources highlight the need for environment-specific evaluation offering insights into neurodiverse teacher experiences.

2.6 GAPS IN THE LITERATURE

Despite AI and its rise in the industry, there is still a notable gap when it comes to its use as a support tool for teachers with ADHD. Most of the studies in the literature focus solely on student outcomes (Holmes et al. 2019; Kumar et al. 2021), and the experiences of teachers in general, with little or no focus on the time management or organizational issues faced by neurodivergent teachers (Barkley 2015; DuPaul and Weyandt 2006).

In addition, there is limited evidence that tools like Magic School AI specifically impacts lesson planning efficiency, work - life balance, and inclusive teaching practices from the view of teachers managing ADHD and family responsibilities (Vogt and Kuhn 2023; Almalki and Alharbi 2021). This evident gap highlights the dire need for more research that can dig deeper than the average teacher's experience of AI, this will observe how emerging technologies like AI can be designed and programmed to support the mental health and well-being, adding to professional development of teachers with ADHD in an impactful way. By Including peer opinions, even if limited in number, one can provide key interpretive insights that help begin to fill these gaps by illuminating individual teacher experiences, which are often overlooked in larger-scale studies. Few empirical studies centres on the lived experiences of teachers, despite the growing presence of AI in education. First person data, which bridge this gap, is delivered in my research notes and journal. Personal insights like editing letters (Jan 17) or drafting inquiry reflections (Feb 7) show how AI lessen the mental effort, enrich theoretical discussions, and ground broader claims.

2.7 HOW THIS STUDY ADDRESSES THE GAPS

This study adds to the literature by looking closely at the lived experiences of a teacher with ADHD and a young family using Magic School AI. Through the qualitative self-study approach, the research provides insights into how the technology of AI tools benefit. How it can support personal work - life

balance by automating administrative tasks such as lesson planning, time management, and differentiated teaching in an inclusive classroom environment. In doing so both the limitations and possibilities of using AI in a practical classroom can be studied. The findings look to enhance both policy and practice and to give useful recommendations for institutions looking to support teachers who are neurodiverse teachers with ADHD. Including the peer interview data introduced an authentic teacher standpoint that substantiates the research and thereby strengthening the relevance and practicality of the findings.

2.8 CHAPTER SUMMARY

The theoretical and practical underpinnings of AI in education, particularly focusing on inclusive teaching practices through frameworks such as UDL and TPACK and considering neurodiverse teachers was established during this literature review.

This study reviewed the key concepts, theoretical frameworks, the findings, and the significant gaps in current research exploring AI tools for neurodivergent teachers. Recent case studies on Magic School AI reinforced the evolving endorsement of AI as a valuable support system in teaching practices. The importance of teacher's voices in shaping the future research and development of AI tools tailored for neurodiverse educators.

CHAPTER 3: THEORIES AND CONCEPTS

While the researcher explored broader literature and emerging themes in AI in education in Chapter 2, the need to isolate the two guiding theoretical frameworks; UDL and TPACK to show how they anchor the research design felt needed in Chapter 3. Here the researcher mapped each framework to the research questions serving as a preview into the thematic analysis in Chapter 5.

Research Question	Mapped Framework
How does Magic School AI influence time management?	TPACK (Technology ↔ Pedagogy)
How does it affect inclusive teaching practices?	UDL (multiple pathways)
What are the teacher's perceptions of student engagement?	UDL + TPACK
What are the benefits/challenges of AI use?	Both frameworks guide this reflection

3.1 UNIVERSAL DESIGN FOR LEARNING (UDL)

By promoting flexibility in teach methods, materials used and assessments to accommodate individual difference in learners UDL provides a theoretical grounding (CAST 2018). In the context of this study, UDL shows how technology can aid a neurodiverse teacher to blend their lessons to fit diverse student needs, whilst also taking care of the cognitive load.

3.2 TECHNOLOGICAL PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TPACK)

The TPACK framework triangulates where the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge come together (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

It is references in this study to help understand how the teacher makes use of AI tools, with regards to their instructional practices. TPACK helps unpack how tools like Magic School AI helps with planning, content delivery and inclusive teaching.

3.3 KEY CONCEPTS

Several concepts were explored during this study:

- **Neurodiversity:** Accepting the fact that neurological differences like ADHD are standard variations of the human brain.
- **AI in Education:** Enhancing teaching and learning practices by incorporating artificial technologies and programs.
- **Inclusive Education:** Educational instruction that aims to assist everyone, all learners, without referencing ability or background.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

INTRODUCTION:

This chapter's main goal was to explore the qualitative research approach used to detail the impact of Magic School AI on the practice of teaching from the vantage point of a teacher who has ADHD and family responsibilities. The methodology included interviews with colleagues, observation, data collection, reflective journaling and more.

4.1 RESEARCH DESIGN:

The primary participant was an ICT teacher with ADHD who also cared for a young child. The qualitative self-study design was employed in this study to harness an in depth understanding of how Magic School AI affected and enhanced lesson planning, classroom management and student engagement.

4.2 RESEARCH PARADIGM

Interpretivism is the primary research paradigm which underpins this study, trailed closely only by constructivism. These two paradigms are at the core of the qualitative research paradigm and are well suited to self-study methodologies.

Interpretivism and constructivism are tied in that they both share a belief that reality is subjective and constructed through the experience of the individual and their interpretations (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Furthermore, knowledge is understood as being co-created by the researcher and participants, the context is shaped by personal history and social interactions. It is an approach which lays emphasis on unique perspectives and points of view of the individuals, shining light on the fact that meaning is perceived as constructed rather than discovered. This study is fundamentally interpretivist/constructivist in nature as it explores the experiences of a teacher with ADHD integrating Magic School AI into her classroom practice. The self-study places the researcher's own interpretations and meaning making at the core of the inquiry. Through various means of data collection like journaling and interviews seeks to understand how the use of AI is experienced, interpreted, and made significant by the teacher in her context.

The interpretivist/constructivist paradigm is a good platform for self-study because it values the subjective views and assumptions of the researcher – participant. The investigator and the subject are also the researcher, and it's in this dynamic that their interpretations, emotions and understandings are central to the process (Pinnegar & Hamilton, 2009).

This paradigm results in a nuanced understanding of the complexities involved in weaving new technologies like Magic School AI in inclusive teaching practice, by allowing for a deep exploration of personal and contextual factors. By leveraging an interpretivist/constructivist stance, this study allows for the individual's voice to be heard, it acknowledges classroom complexities and generates insights which are meaningful.

4.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

4.3.1 QUALITATIVE SELF-STUDY METHODOLOGY

A qualitative self-study method was chosen to allow for deep reflection on the researchers teaching practice while integrating AI, ADHD, and family responsibilities. To be both a researcher and participant, makes it possible to offer meaningful and rich insights (Samaras, 2011; LaBoskey, 2004).

Reflective journaling logs was used to exam how Magic School AI supported or challenged their teaching and personal life. On going reflection inherent in self-study aligned with the researchers' goal to improving on their professional practice. An external peer interview added an outside perspective to personal observations supporting triangulation.

4.3.2 OVERVIEW AND KEY SCHOLARS

Qualitative research methodology that has become increasingly influential in education. Advanced self-study has been defined as rigorous, reflective and a systematic approach for educators to examine and improve their own practice by seminal scholars such as Loughran (2004), Hamilton and Pinnegar (1998), and LaBoskey (2004). Self-study is “about the improvement of practice, about better understanding of that practice, and about sharing that understanding with others.” Loughran (2004). Hamilton and Pinnegar (1998) further point out that self-study is rooted in the context of the researcher’s own environment and is made to generate knowledge which is both informative in a broader sense but also personally meaningful Loughran (2004) argues that self-study, in order to enable educators to generate knowledge through a reflective practice that is rooted in their teaching context, has to be both personal and systematic.

The researcher positioned themselves uniquely to explore AI both through a practical and ethical lens by volunteering to lead their school’s AI Committee, in addition to participation in the Middle States RAIL course.

4.3.3 COMPONENTS OF SELF-STUDY

1. Self as Inquirer

The main tenant of the self-study is that the researcher is both the investigator and the participant (LaBoskey, 2004). Deeper personal perspective and insights are allowed for, and the researcher’s beliefs, actions and experiences are central to the inquiry. This study is one where the teacher-researcher explores her own experience as a teacher with ADHD, with a young family using Magic School AI to support lesson planning and inclusive teaching.

2. Reflexivity

At the heart of the self-study is critical self-reflection (Loughran, 2004; Samaras, 2011). An honest examination of one's own assumptions, biases and professional growth is involved in this type of reflection. Through journaling, the researcher could interrogate not only the outcomes of the AI tools but also her own fears, responses, challenges, and understandings.

3. Systematic Inquiry

Self-study is a personal affair, but it is also rigorous and methodical (LaBoskey, 2004).

The process of gathering data must be both transparent and organized. In this study the data, analysed for recurring patterns and themes, includes reflective journals, classroom observations and interviews with colleagues.

4. Purpose: Improving Practice and Contributing to Knowledge

The dual purpose of the self-study is not only to enhance the researchers own practice but also to contribute to the wider knowledge base of teaching and teacher education (Loughran, 2004; Hamilton & Pinnegar, 1998). Through this self-research approach the researcher aims to enhance her teaching practice whilst offering insights into the subject which can inform and inspire other educators, especially those suffering from ADHD and who may have family responsibilities.

Justification for Choosing Self-Study

Self-study is particularly appropriate for this research for several reasons:

Alignment with Research Focus: The study would like to shed light of the lived experience of a teacher, managing ADHD integrating AI into her practice. Self-study does make way for the exploration of nuanced, specific challenges that are best resolved from an insider's perspective (Loughran, 2004).

Depth and Authenticity: Self-study does give a rich, authentic data set by focusing on the researcher's voice and experience. This is vital when looking at the intersection of personal tribulations (ADHD and family responsibilities) and professional innovation or growth (AI integration).

Reflexive Professional Growth: This method champions ongoing professional learning and adaptation and runs parallel to improving the researchers own practice and the idea of sharing findings with the bigger educational community (Samaras, 2011).

Contribution to Teacher Education: Self-study stands as a valid approach for gaining practical knowledge that can inform teacher education, policy, and practice (Hamilton & Pinnegar, 1998).

Phases of the Study

The research progressed in various interconnected stages.

Preparation and Orientation:

- First getting to grips with Magic School AI tool and the preparation of a journaling template.
- Looking at research objectives and ethical considerations.
- Implementation and Data Generation.
- Using Magic School AI for lesson planning, classroom organization, and behaviour interventions daily.
- Reflective journaling after each lesson to remember insights and record immediate experiences.
- Student engagement metrics during AI assisted lessons in an observational manner.
- Interviews, with peers making use of AI tools.

Reflection and Analysis:

- Looking at patterns, challenges, and successes of the journal entries periodically.
- Thematic analysis to bring together findings and formulate research questions and objectives.
- Evaluation and Adjustment.
- Looking at the practice and evaluating it based on insights gained.
- Adjusting if necessary to AI tool usage and strategies in the classroom based on reflection.
- Preparation of findings and formulating them to be shared with larger community

The Cyclical Nature: Reflection, Action, and Evaluation

- A fundamental of this self-study design lies in its cyclical nature, running parallel to the model of reflective practice (Schön, 1983; Loughran, 2004).
- Action: Using Magic School AI daily in teaching tasks.
- Reflection: Critically reflecting on each experience through journaling and observation.
- Evaluation: Evaluating or assessing the success of these actions via implementation on teaching efficiency, student engagement and personal well - being.
- The ongoing cycle makes sure that the researcher continues growth and professional improvement.

Justification of the Design

- This design is very appropriate for the study's aim exactly because it is qualitative, exploratory, and cyclical.
- Makes possible a detailed exploration of the lived experience of a teacher who is struggling with ADHD and family responsibilities.
- It tracks the context-specific nature of the integration of technology in classrooms.
- It backs the iterative process of learning, reflecting, and acting.
- It produces good data which can help teachers in their practice but also inform the general educational discourse.

Time Period and Structure: Cross-Sectional with Cyclical Elements

The study is cross sectional in nature; the data was collected during a limited period of one school semester giving a glimpse of the account during the implementation of Magic School AI. Recurring elements however also form part of it, typical is a self-study and reflective practice.

The study highlighted repeated cycles of action using Magic School AI, reflection, journaling, analysis, and evaluation adjusting practice and analysis outcomes, aligning with the iterative nature of professional developments and progress (Loughran, 2004).

CONCLUSION

In summary, qualitative self-study, as said by Loughran, Hamilton, LaBoskey, and others, is an established methodology which is rigorous. One that foregrounds the researchers' experience, reflexivity, and inquiry. Its emphasis on improving the daily teaching practice and generating data which is helpful for the community is well suited for this investigation of Magic School AI's impact on the teaching practices of an educator who is dealing with ADHD and family life.

This study uses a qualitative research design, with emphasis on utilizing a self-study approach. This type of research is well suited for looking at complex, context driven phenomena and for looking deeper into lived subjective experiences of the participants (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

The design is primarily of an exploratory nature, investigating how Magic School AI influences teaching practices, organization, and student engagement of a teacher managing ADHD and family responsibilities - an area which has not been researched enough to date. It is also said to be descriptive as it tries to catalogue the processes, experiences and outcomes tied to the integration of AI tools in the classroom.

4.4 DATA GENERATION METHODS:

Data was collected through a variety of means (Please reference to Appendix A and Appendix B for the peer interview data and the AI Usage Logbook).

Reflective Journaling:

The researcher's evolving understanding and critical reflections throughout the research period was primarily captured through the reflective journaling. This journaling was composed of both structured and unstructured elements. Whilst allowing for open - ended, free form reflection, each entry started with a prompt that guaranteed consistency and focus on key elements in the research, amongst them time management, student engagements and lesson planning. Questions like "How did Magic School AI assist with lesson planning or classroom organization today?", "Did the use of Magic School AI save me time or reduce stress?" and "What challenges or insights did I experience when using the AI tool?" The approach was good because it allowed for targeted experiences and unexpected ones. Anything could happen and that was documented through the journaling.

Daily entries were recorded on days when Magic School AI was used and continued for a period (one school term) and this allowed for a rich detailed longitudinal account of the integration process. This journaling process not only collected data systemically but also allowed for a deep reflection, making it possible for the researcher to examine with a keen eye the impact of AI on the teaching practice, personal well-being, and student engagement.

Semi Structured Interviews:

Interview conducted with peer who use AI tools in their classroom to gain extra perspectives as well as to validate the findings from reflective journaling. The interviews were done in a semi structured format to allow for flexibility as well as guided inquiry. Questions included: “How has incorporating AI tools like Magic School AI influenced your planning or classroom management?”, “What advantages or challenges have you come across as a teacher using AI?”, and “Has AI supported your efforts to create a more inclusive classroom environment, in what ways?”

Participants were selected by focusing on teachers who have experience with using AI tools. This method ensured interviews provided were relevant to the insights that aided the primary self-study data and provided a more rounded considerate understandings of AI influence on education.

Due to time constraints and the lack of additional willing participants, only one interview was completed. This was administered through a Google Form, allowing flexibility to suit the participant's schedule. While the interview data was limited, it provided insight that complemented and contrasted the researcher's own reflections. This method of data capturing aligns with the self-study practice, where the researcher's own experience is the principal element of investigation, and the depth of the study is prioritized over scale (LaBoskey, 2004; Loughran, 2004).

Beyond triangulation, several strategies were employed to ensure credibility and trustworthiness: Reflective inquiry was the root of this study. Informal but consistent peer debriefing took place with a trusted colleague experienced in Magic School AI, assisting in confronting assumptions and reduce interpretive bias. The Analytical process of journal logs, coding records and observational notes to maintain an audit trail, ensuring traceability and transparency throughout.

Due to the single external interview, saturated data could not be established recurring themes were evident around time-saving affordances, classroom engagement, emotional impact, and instructional alignment. Lastly, through systematic reflection, methodological transparency, and peer feedback, the study remained credible, ethical, and authentic.

Implementation of Magic School AI:

The use of Magic School AI was incorporated in the daily working and designs of lesson plans, scaffold assignments and in general to manage classroom behaviour effectively. Magic School AI was used to simplify and organize personal and classroom tasks.

Role of the Researcher:

In this self-study, the researcher served as primary data source and analysis, drawing on both roles as a teacher with ADHD and as a parent. This provided deep insight into the lived realities of integrating Magic School AI into daily life but also introduced potential bias. To manage subjectivity, the researcher employed regular, analytical self-reflection through journaling, unambiguously acknowledging assumptions and emotions as they occurred. Triangulation was achieved by accompanying self-reflection with schoolroom observations and discussions and interviews with peers, providing alternate viewpoints, and assisting in validating the outcomes. By keeping an audit trail and addressing the researchers bias, ensure transparency, and authenticity, adding valuable insights to inclusive, AI-supported teaching.

4.5 DATA ANALYSIS:

The information from journal entries and interviews were analysed thematically to look for patterns which related to teaching effectiveness, the efficiency of the organization and student engagement. This tracking aimed to reveal the patterns and themes in how AI tools impact a teacher's flow. The time saved on lesson planning as a qualitative measure was also tracked and recorded.

Validity and Trustworthiness:

To achieve credible and meaningful findings, it is essential to ensure the validity and trustworthiness of the research. To strengthen the rigour of its design and analysis the study employed several strategies.

Triangulation:

Data were collected from multiple sources, including daily reflective journal entries, classroom observations, and semi-structured interviews with fellow teachers who use AI tools.

Triangulation was achieved in the following way.

The study was able to enhance the credibility of its findings and reduce the risk of bias or overreliance on a single perspective through comparing and cross-referencing insights from these various methods.

For example, the patterns in student engagement during lessons which were AI assisted lessons were checked and validated by both their teacher's reflections and the feedback from colleagues. This provided a comprehensive understanding of the influence of Magic School AI. An example of this was that the engagement of students during AI-assisted lessons was fed back and validated by both the researcher and colleagues. This, in turn, provided a more rigid understanding of the influence of Magic School AI.

Reflexivity:

A core component of the research process was reflexivity. Personal biases, assumptions and evolving perspectives were critically examined by the researcher regularly using journal entries. Reflections such as "I felt I was more positive about AI today after a good lesson" or "My frustration with time management may have affected how I regarded the tool's effectiveness" were common. The researcher's positionality was acknowledged and managed throughout the study through this ongoing and constant self-examination.

Peer Interview:

This consisted of speaking and conversing with a trusted co-teacher who had a good background knowledge and experience of AI in education and qualitative research. These meetings typically occurred twice a week if the opportunity presented itself and usually focused on challenging the researchers' interpretations, questioning themes that may have emerged and discussing the data and the explanations attached to them. In this way, blind spots were identified, and the credibility of the study was strengthened by the external check on the analysis.

Audit Trail:

An audit trail was kept throughout the research process to ensure credibility and replicability.

Thematic matrices, analytical memos documenting interpretive decisions and the preservation of raw data (journal entries, observational notes, etc) were all included. There was a clear account of how findings were reached through this comprehensive logging of documents, which instilled the overall trustworthiness of the study. The interplay between triangulation reflexivity, conversations with colleagues and a detailed audit ensured the findings were dependable and grounded in a research process that was transparent.

4.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

Ethical Considerations: The Data Security and Researchers Well-Being

Researcher Well-Being and Emotional Challenges

The well - being of the researcher was a central ethical consideration considering the self - study nature of this research. As both the primary participant and the investigator - a teacher managing ADHD and family responsibilities - there was an obvious risk of emotional challenges, stress or fatigue and anxiety from the dual demands of professional reflection and personal disclosure. The process can surface different and difficult emotions, self-doubt and even burnt out considering the process critically examines one's own teaching practices.

STRATEGIES FOR SELF-CARE AND SUPPORT

To address these risks, several self-care strategies were implemented:

- **Scheduled Reflection:** Journal entries were conducted at consistent and manageable times (immediately after lesson or at the end of the day) with a flexibility to skip entries or to pause if the emotional stress it too much.
- **Emotional Boundaries:** When it comes to frequency and the depth of personal reflection the researcher sets clear boundaries. This ensures the ability to step back and seek distance from emotionally charged topics.
- **Seeking Support:** A safe space was created with a trusted peer to discuss and debrief if the emotional load got too much. The option of professional counselling through the school was available if desired.

- Mindfulness and Self-Compassion: The researcher was an avid follower of yoga, breathing and mindfulness techniques and understands and accepts that vulnerability and emotional struggle are natural aspects of self-study.

4.7 RIGOUR AND TRUSTWORTHINESS

The Protection of the privacy and data of the research was an import.

- Digital Storage: Password secured protected storage kept all the data, journal entries, notes, and interviews records.
- Anonymization: All names and references to colleagues, students or school information were removed in all records.
- Access Control: Only the researcher had access.
- Data Retaining and Disposal: Data will be kept until it is no more necessary, and there after shredded and permanently deleted.

4.8 CONCLUSION

This study prioritized the well-being of the researcher. In addition, by protecting the names of those involved, protecting the data and the management of it, the report guaranteed the care, integrity, and respect for everyone involved.

This chapter examined the influence of Magic School AI on teaching practices and student engagement through a comprehensive research methodology. It detailed the data collection, implementation procedures, analysis, and the ethical considerations. Providing a full-bodied framework of data which upholds the ethical standards and the reliability.

CHAPTER 5: FINDINGS AND REFLECTIONS-INTEGRATION OF MAGIC SCHOOL AI

5.1 INTRODUCTION:

This chapter looks at the findings from the researcher's reflective journal, one peer interview and general classroom observations. It explores how the use of Magic School AI influenced time management, lesson planning, student engagement, inclusive teaching, and learning practices all from the perspective of a teacher with ADHD.

Themes conformed to the study's research questions and were interpreted through the lenses of TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) and UDL (Universal Design for Learning). Thematic analysis was used to code and group the data.

The benefits and challenges encountered are discussed in this chapter and the findings align with existing literature. This interpretive analysis aims to ask why these patterns emerged and what they mean for inclusive and digitally supported teaching practices. The study's objectives are addressed with evidence-based insights and data. Mostly the data was collected through reflective journaling to look at how AI was used in the classroom and what the impact of its use was. The cycles of reflection, action, and adjustment (Loughran, 2004) informed the structure and nature of interpretation.

5.2 THE STRUCTURE OF THE JOURNALING PROCESS

Captured primarily through the reflective journaling were the researcher's evolving understanding and critical reflections.

This journaling was composed of both structured and unstructured elements. Whilst allowing for open-ended, free form reflection, each entry started with a prompt that guaranteed consistency and focus on key elements in the research, amongst them time management, student engagements and lesson planning. Questions like

- "How did Magic School AI assist with lesson planning or classroom organization today?"
- "Did the use of Magic School AI save me time or reduce stress?"
- "What challenges or insights did I experience when using the AI tool?"

This approach ensured the capturing of both outcomes, offering rich qualitative data over a longitudinal period (January 6 – March 30, excluding school breaks). On days when the AI tool was

used, journal entries captured a realistic reflection on its integrations into teaching, serving as both a method of data collection and proficient reflection, observing the impact of it on teaching. To ensure accuracy and transparency, initial open coding was applied to reflective journals, followed by subgrouping into overarching themes.

The chart below outlines the thematic coding process:

UDL and TPACK frameworks were used to interpret themes to strengthen the study.

5.3 THEMATIC CONCLUSIONS FROM THE JOURNALS

(Please reference to Appendix A and Appendix B for the peer interview data and the AI Usage Logbook)

5.3.1 THEME 1: TIME EFFICIENCY

A consistent observation was the significant amount of time saved in planning. Magic School AI reduced planning time on average up to 50%, mostly for lesson planning and differentiation in instruction and behavioural interventions. The AI Usage Logbook (Appendix A) recorded that on between 40 and 60 min was saved on averaged when Magic School AI was used for lesson planning.

"When I used Magic School to proofread and give student feedback and comments, I consistently saved 1- or 2-hours' time that I could instead spend with my child." — Reflective Journal Entry, January 13 & 24, 2025

The above aligns with other research stating how AI reduces teachers' cognitive load and free up time for to focus on students (Holmes et al., 2019; Baradari et al, 2025). This theme supports TPACK's emphasis on how AI tool enhance pedagogical efficiency by means of technology (Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Simultaneously, from a UDL standpoint, the adaptability and flexibility offered by AI supports multiple means of engagement, allowing educators to meet diverse learner needs at the same time also reduce the strain of lesson planning allowing educators to allot more time to other aspects of teaching and personal life that is vital for those managing ADHD with caregiving obligations (CAST, 2018).

5.3.2 THEME 2: TEACHER WELL-BEING AND STRESS REDUCTION

A strong connection between AI usage and reduced emotional strain was suggested by the research journal entries. On High AI reliant days there was a reduction noticed on the self-reported stress rating inputs in the AI Usage Log, on average dropped from 6/10 to 3/10 on AI reliant days.

"I did not feel as mentally drained to use AI Magic School to assist in the rubric generation, even though I had to alter here and there it was great to have a framework to prevent me from overthinking. Reducing anxiety, I regularly feel when creating it from scratch especially with limited time" -Journal Entry, January 23, 2025

This theme directly relates to UDL guides on assisting educators' adaptability by providing tools that reduce mental impediments (Almalki and Alharbi, 2021).

Student productivity gains have been widely noted (Khan et al., 2024), however this study aims to span the dialogue by directing focus on how these AI tool impact the teacher's wellbeing and administrative load in the true inclusive classroom.

5.3.3 THEME 3: IMPROVED DIFFERENTIATION

By Generating resources for scaffolding fast, Magic School AI supported the teacher in real time to have the ability to differentiate in a diverse classroom.

"With the help of Magic School AI's adaptive suggestions, I created a few versions of the same task, without having to explain or restart from scratch for each level. Making it possible to meet my students at where they were"- Reflective Journal Entry, January 30th ,2025."

These findings demonstrate UDL principles—offering numerous methods of engagement and representation (CAST, 2018). It also lessens mental load for neurodivergent teachers during lesson preparation.

5.3.4 THEME 4: STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

There were observations made by the teacher that those lessons that were prepared or generated with assistance of Magic School AI, especially the interactive, inquiry-based lessons were more successful.

"The students showed curiosity and were more responsive and focused when I used AI-generated discussion prompts—it inspired them, they were interested and I didn't anticipate they would be."- Journal Entry, February 6, 2025

These findings reflect other studies that suggest AI supported tools in education motivates and sparks interest, in STEAM/ STEAM subjects, it also reflects more interest among marginalized learners (Chalkiadakis et al. 2024). From a TPACK outlook, AI enhances content delivery while maintaining educator's control.

5.3.5 THEME 5: LIMITATIONS AND ETHICAL CONCERNS

There were limitations despite all the many benefits of using AI as an educator with ADHD. Sometimes it took a while to insert the perfect prompt and sometimes the AI tool generated very generic responses, and many times re-prompting to make the tool understand what was needed to match the framework that was needed to instruct. There were also the underlying data privacy concerns and feeling of over-reliance on the tool that left one feeling out of control in some ways.

"I felt that my voice wasn't getting through, the tone of the output disagreed with mine. Human tone matters more than speed." -Journal Entry, 16 January 2025)

The tensions between authenticity and efficiency, is highlighted here, especially for neurodiverse teachers who see the worth in authentic individual tone. Ethical concerns included data privacy, over-reliance, and the cultural alignment of generated content (Williamson & Eynon, 2020). The findings suggest that contextualization and human oversight are crucial whilst incorporating AI in education.

5.4 THE REFLECTIVE CYCLE: ACTION, REFLECTION, ADJUSTMENT

There was a clear repetitive pattern of reflection throughout the journaling process.

→ the use of Magic School AI → Finding the right prompt → Reading and evaluating the output → Testing and adjusting the practice where needed.

For instance, initially there was an over-reliance on AI-generated lessons, and then a more blended approach was incorporated by using AI tools to develop or spark lesson ideas rather than creating them in entirety. This way it was truly more personalized and authentic for the learners and for teacher's ownership of the work. These patterns align with Samaras' (2011) emphasis on reflective cycles during self-study research.

5.4.1 CROSS-THEME TENSIONS AND INSIGHTS

While the tools of Magic School AI, offered clear benefits in assisting with differentiation and timesaving, it also presented emotional and ethical complexities. For example, even though lesson planning was streamlined (Theme 1), some concerns were noted over the authenticity, relatability, and the delivery tone (Theme 5). Correspondingly, the improvement of student engagement (Theme 4) depended on the educator's insightfulness in choosing which AI content to use. This type of tension proves the key finding: that efficient AI integration continuously needs critical consideration and reflection especially for neurodiverse teachers navigating both technological and emotional challenges. Supporting the call for inclusive pedagogical tools that resonates with the educators working conditions and identity (Flavian, 2016).

5.5 SUMMARY

The researcher's findings express how AI tools in particular, Magic School AI can be used as a meaningful support system or co-teaching tool for teachers who have ADHD and caregiving responsibilities by reducing stress and saving time to enhance productivity. Nevertheless, critical teacher oversight remains necessary to avoid ethical risks and ensure reliable content (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Holmes et al., 2022). The AI Log spreadsheet that provides a corresponding data record that validates the qualitative insights with measurable trends in stress reduction and in timesaving (see Appendix A). This focusses in this chapter were on how AI, when aligned with UDL and TPACK, can empower inclusive and supportive teaching when educators preserve agency over its use (CAST, 2018; Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

(Appendix A and B includes the full AI Usage Log Spreadsheet and the google form interview referenced in this chapter).

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 CONCLUSION

This self – study examines how Magic School AI positively affected the professional practices of a teacher managing attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and family responsibilities. The integration of AI influenced into daily routines such as planning, time management and inclusive pedagogy showed a positive effect. Magic School AI contributed to improved focus, decreased stress, and a more responsive lesson delivery by automating repetitive administrative tasks and offering structured planning support.

AI technologies, when used purposefully, can reduce the workload of educators whilst promoting inclusive and efficient planning approaches, and the outcomes of this study align with this view (Holmes et al. 2019; Zawacki-Richter et al. 2019). The Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework brought a very useful platform, as the AI tool helped with content creation that was flexible and instruction strategies which were differentiated (CAST 2018; Choi 2024).

The previous findings that teachers with ADHD benefit from structured organisational systems and support which is scaffolded to manage their professional tasks is supported by the lived experience documented in this study (Flavian 2016; DuPaul and Weyandt 2006). An increase in perceived self - efficacy and emotional regulation on days when AI was used is revealed by the reflective journals. This suggests that the AI tool influenced the teacher's professional functioning which was stabilizing (Almalki and Alharbi 2021).

Concerns were also identified. The generic content produced by the AI on occasions needed serious prompt refinement and lacked in addition, the alignment with tone and content that the teacher needed. These findings mirror the existing literature that heeds a warning against the excessive overreliance on AI and instead calls for the ethical oversight and contextual sensitivity in educational tools (Williamson and Eynon 2020; European Commission 2024). By focusing on the under - researched intersection of neurodivergence, AI use and teacher workload management, this study contributes to the growing discourse on teacher inclusion. The research stays context specific, but it does provide actionable insights for teachers, developers, and policy makers to further teaching through inclusive technological supports (Vogt and Kuhn 2023).

6.2 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This report is subject to various limitations:

- The limited number of participants: Merely one peer interview was conducted, restricting external substantiation of the argument and triangulation.
- Bias in self-reporting: Due to the fact that the researcher's personal reflections, observations and experiences were used, subjectivity could be introduced.
- The data collection period was short: Long term sustained impacts or patterns were limited or restricted since only one school terms was used in the report.
- Platform-specific focus: The report examined and addressed Magic School AI's influence. The results might not be similar for different AI platform with other outcomes and experiences.

Without undermining the study's value, these findings underscore the need for a bigger, more diverse research to strengthen the evidence base around AI and teacher neurodiversity.

6.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

6.3.1 For Educators with ADHD and Family Responsibilities

For those teachers who experience symptoms of ADHD and who are managing multiple life demands, it is encouraged to explore AI tools in their daily routines as an organizational support. Magic School AI can assist with administrative tasks and planning (Angelone and Burton 2024). However, AI should not be used without critically analysing and prompting. Teachers must curate and remain analytical by adapting, reviewing, and relating to AI outputs to preserve authentic and professional voice and align with the actual students' requirements (Williamson & Eynon, 2020).

Teachers must engage in ongoing reflective practices, such as journaling and student/peer discussions, to fully evaluate AI's impact on workflow, emotional regulation, and classroom dynamics (Samaras 2011).

6.3.2 For School Leaders and Policymakers

The strengthening and steady incorporation of AI literacy within professional development initiatives, to ensure teachers are well equipped to confidently engage with emerging technologies. Aligning with the TPACK framework, which highlights the connection of technological, content and pedagogical

knowledge (Mishra & Koehler, 2006), and encourages OECD (2023) suggestions that note how important it is to equip teachers with the skills required to implement AI ethically and efficiently in diverse classroom settings. A truly inclusive workplace should recognize the cognitive diversity of their teaching staff. School leaders should provide training, AI literacy, including ethical use which would promote adaptive planning and responsible data engagement (OECD 2023; TeachAI 2024). This awareness directly informed the school-wide AI policy developed during my participation in the RAIL course, ensuring that real-world schoolroom requirements were represented in the formal decision-making

Policies should accommodate and incorporate teachers who are neurodiverse, like teachers with ADHD and other neurodiversity's. These should be included in institutional planning. The school culture should foster adaptive scheduling, peer tutoring and reflective practice time.

6.3.3 For Educational Technology Developers

AI tools which offer flexibility, application creators and developers should prioritize user customization and ethical principles. Tools should offer personalized tone, content structure and pacing which fits the classroom contexts (Vogt and Kuhn 2023). In addition, there should be transparency concerning data privacy, bias moderation, and teacher ownership of the materials used in the platform design (European Commission 2024).

A conversation between educators, including neurodivergent voices - during the design's evolution, should take place to ensure that tools are created that are pedagogically sound and socially responsive to diverse needs.

6.3.4 Recommendations for Future Research:

- Conduct mixed method continuing research study to assess the longterm impact of AI tools like Magic School AI on teacher with ADHD.
- AI's role in supporting other neurodiverse conditions, such as dyslexia, anxiety, and autism, should be investigated to extend inclusive teaching research (Almalki and Alharbi, 2021).
- Learners' viewpoints, especially on how AI-assisted lessons influence student engagement, differentiation outcomes, and classroom dynamics should be considered (Chalkiadakis et al., 2024).
- Establish or critically reassess school-wide AI implementation frameworks, including the school's culture, leadership approaches, and policy expansions to consider effective AI integration.

These recommendations can assist in creating responsible practices and promote progression in inclusive AI use in education.

6.4 FINAL REFLECTION

This research confirms that AI technologies, when used with critical engagement can offer meaningful support to neurodiverse educators. Magic School AI added tremendous value in supporting the researcher who manages ADHD and family responsibilities by providing structure and reducing planning strain.

The effective support AI offers lies not in automation alone, but in its considerate and ethical integration. AI cannot replace professional judgment or human interaction, instead, it must act as a co-teacher, supporting without replacing authenticity. Practice and policy development must be guided by the inclusive support for teachers, as the field of education continues to adapt to technical innovation. This report forms part of the researcher's wider professional ambitions, reiterating the researcher's pledge to inclusive, contemplative, and ethical AI implementation in teaching including leadership in developing school-wide AI policies and their preparation through the Middle States RAIL endorsement course.

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APPENDIX A

Date	Task	Magic School AI Tool Used	Time Saved (Est.)	Family-Friendly Notes	Reflections
Jan 6, 2025	Unit Standards Unpacking	Academic Content Generator	None	NA	AI didn't align with curriculum needs. Reaffirmed value of manual planning.
Jan 7, 2025	Proofreading & Editing	Text Rewriter	1 hour	Time spent with my child instead	AI helped quickly spot grammar errors. Still needed to adjust for tone and content relevance.
Jan 8, 2025	Rubric Generation	Rubric Generator	None	NA	Good for brainstorming, but still had to write most parts.
Jan 9, 2025	Student Feedback Drafting	Text Dependent Questions	2 hours	Helped me leave school on time	Sentence starters saved time. Tone still generic.
Jan 10, 2025	Real-World Task Design	Informational Texts	30 mins	NA	Didn't align with inquiry theme. Prompting needs refining.
Jan 13, 2025	Rubric Generation	Rubric Generator	2 hours	Reduced stress at home	Too vague. Better results by starting from scratch.
Jan 14, 2025	Feedback Scaffolding	Assignment Scaffolder	1 hour	Helped me leave school on time	Tone was robotic. Harder to personalize.
Jan 15, 2025	Lesson Plan Development	SE Model Science Lesson Plan Generator	1 hour	Time spent with my child instead	AI suggestions didn't meet my objectives.
Jan 16, 2025	Rubric Generation	Rubric Generator	30 mins	NA	AI gave usable framework, needed tweaking.
Jan 17, 2025	Editing Parent Letters	Text Rewriter	2 hours	Fixed up weekend time	AI helped with formatting and clarity. Needed manual content revision.
Jan 18, 2025	Generated negotiation weekly dinner plan that suits a toddler and adult	Lesson Planning Wizard	45 mins	anxiety reduced	The AI made meal planning easier, which freed up mental energy and improved our weekly routines.
Jan 20, 2025	Email Drafting	Class Newsletter Tool	45 mins	Left work early, time spent with my child instead	Reduced overthinking. Clearer phrasing.
Jan 21, 2025	Classroom Expectations Doc	Text Rewriter	30 mins	Reduced after-hours prep	Useful for structure, needed tone adjustment.
Jan 22, 2025	Inquiry Planning Ideas	Academic Content Generator	1 hour	Allowed evening family time	The AI provided inspiration, but I needed to adapt the ideas to better fit our unit plan.
Jan 23, 2025	Anchor Chart Titles	Text Rewriter	15 mins	NA	Saved brainstorming time. Easy to adapt.
Jan 24, 2025	Exit Ticket Creation	Multiple Choice Assessments	30 mins	Reduced prep fatigue	Templates helpful but required editing.
Jan 27, 2025	Scaffolding Tasks	Assignment Scaffolder	None	NA	AI misunderstood learning goals.
Jan 28, 2025	Lesson Outline	SE Model Science Lesson Plan Generator	1 hour	Reduced morning prep	Good initial layout. Adjusted for pacing.
Jan 29, 2025	Visual Aid Suggestions	Informational Texts	30 mins	Helped reduce screen time at home	Gave image ideas. I still had to create them manually.
Jan 30, 2025	Inquiry Task Drafting	Academic Content Generator	45 mins	Left work earlier	Helped shape activities aligned with learning outcomes.
Jan 31, 2025	Group Roles Template	Group Work Generator	1 hour	Allowed time for errands	Gave structure quickly. Minor edits needed.
Feb 3, 2025	Assessment Description	Multiple Choice Assessments	30 mins	Reduced mental load	The draft created by AI lacked the necessary clarity and precision, so I had to make significant revisions to ensure it met the required standard.
Feb 4, 2025	Learning Objectives Draft	Academic Content Generator	None	NA	
Feb 4, 2025	Created a daily routine template with toddler activities and breaks	Schedule Builder	1 hour	Time spent with my child instead	The suggestions provided by the AI were not well-aligned with my needs, so I ended up returning to my own manual approach.
Feb 5, 2025	Parent Communication Draft	Class Newsletter Tool	45 mins	Gave time to prep dinner	Gave me structure, so my days felt less chaotic. It made things easier with my ADHD and helped keep our routine on track.
Feb 6, 2025	Student Worksheet Template	Informational Texts	30 mins	Time spent with my child instead	Efficient wording suggestions.
Feb 7, 2025	Inquiry Reflection Draft	Text Dependent Questions	1 hour	Helped mental clarity	Helped structure, but didn't match level of differentiation.
Feb 10, 2025	Choice Board Tasks	Choice Board Generator (UDL)	45 mins	Reduced afternoon planning	Good prompts for student reflections.
Feb 11, 2025	Feedback on Group Work	Text Rewriter	None	NA	Helped generate differentiated options.
Feb 12, 2025	Anchor Chart Working	Text Rewriter	15 mins	Allowed quiet evening	Tone didn't match class culture.
Feb 13, 2025	Rubric Revisions	Rubric Generator	30 mins	saved time so could help with bedtime routine	Gave great starter ideas.
Feb 14, 2025	Self-Assessment Prompts	Text Dependent Questions	1 hour	Reduced weekend prep	The AI was useful for reviewing the clarity of my rubric language.
Feb 17, 2025	Email Responses	Class Newsletter Tool	45 mins	Left school on time	AI suggestions were creative and inclusive.
Feb 18, 2025	Vocabulary List Generation	Vocabulary List Generator	30 mins	Helped me spend more time reading	Helped reduce time drafting sensitive responses.
Feb 19, 2025	Exit Ticket Questions	Multiple Choice Assessments	30 mins	Reduced prep fatigue	Aligned well with unit. Easy to tweak.
Feb 24, 2025	Brainstormed holiday activities for a 3-year-old with minimal screen time	Date Generator	30 mins	bonding time with my child	AI gave fresh, developmentally appropriate ideas. Planning ahead reduced anxiety and improved quality time.
Mar 6, 2025	Sourced beginner yoga and breathing exercises to manage daily stress	Wellness Routine Assistant	30 mins	Helped me stay calm and present for my family	AI mindfulness tips helped me chill out and stay relaxed during hectic days.

APPENDIX B

Confidentiality

All information collected during this study will be kept confidential. Your identity will not be disclosed, and any identifying information will be removed or anonymized in the final report. Data will be securely stored and only accessible to the researcher.

Consent

By signing this form, you acknowledge that:

You have read and understood the information provided above.

You have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.

You voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.

Participant's Name: _____

Participant's Signature: _____

Date: _____

|
Researcher's Signature: _____

Date: _____

Title of Study: Improving Lesson Planning for Teachers with ADHD: A Study of Magic School AI's Influence on Time Management and Inclusivity

Researcher: Jeanne van Heerden

Institution: Stadio PTY LTD

email: 21206811@stadio.ac.za

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to explore how the integration of Magic School AI affects teaching practices and student engagement from the perspective of an ICT PYP teacher with ADHD and a young family. Your participation will help provide insights into the benefits and challenges associated with using AI tools in educational settings.

Participation

You are invited to participate in this study because you are an educator who uses or is interested in using Magic School AI in your teaching practice. Participation is entirely voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time without any questions.

Procedures

If you agree to participate, you might be asked to:

Engage in an informal interview about your experiences with Magic School AI. You also might be asked to allow classroom observations during lessons where Magic School AI is utilised.

Risks and Benefits

There are minimal risks associated with participating in this study. However, discussing personal experiences may trigger some feelings of discomfort. Support resources will be available if needed. The potential benefits include contributing to research that may enhance teaching practices and support teachers.

Google Form Interview:

1/10/2023, 1:11 PM

Exploring the Use of Magic School AI in Inclusive Teaching

Exploring the Use of Magic School AI in Inclusive Teaching

1 response

[Publish analytics](#)

How many years of teaching experience do you have?

[Copy](#)

1 response

What grade(s) or age group(s) do you teach?

1 response

Reception

Are you currently using any AI tools in your teaching practice?

[Copy](#)

1 response

Teaching & AI Use

In what ways do you use Magic School AI in your lesson planning or classroom practice?

1 response

With lesson plan and song generator.

Can you describe a recent lesson where you used Magic School AI?

1 response

The life cycle of a butterfly.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1LiHqWNTN1mgQ2xPlomin4vAbTFGOjvpx1RRtAgLvDz/viewanalytics>

1/2

Exploring the Use of Magic School AI in Inclusive Teaching

Which Magic School AI features do you find most helpful?

Copy

1 response

Time Management & ADHD Support

Has Magic School AI helped you manage your time more effectively? If so, how?

1 response

It gives comprehensive lesson plans that you can add too and edit.

How has AI impacted your overall workload or ability to balance teaching and personal life?

1 response

Planning has become easier. Good for writing letters to parents. Not in my personal life.

Inclusion & Engagement

Have you noticed any changes in student engagement since using Magic School AI?

1 response

Magic School AI has enabled more tailored learning experiences that reflect the varied abilities and interests identified in our student profiles.

Do you believe the AI supports inclusive teaching practices in your context? Please explain.

1 response

Absolutely, AI can be a powerful tool to support inclusive teaching practices within our Early Years context and our play-based, inquiry-driven approach.

Concerns, Reflections & Suggestions

Have you faced any challenges or ethical concerns when using AI (e.g., tone, data privacy, content accuracy)?

1 response

Not really as I delete content I'm not 100% sure about.

Do AI-generated outputs always align with your teaching style or values? Why or why not?

1 response

Not always, that's why it's a starting point for me and I adapt it to suit my teaching.

What advice would you offer to another teacher considering using AI in their practice?

1 response

Always read everything it produces and if you are not sure of something delete it. Put in as much information and PYP language to get a good result.

1 response

 Copy

What improvements or changes would you suggest for Magic School AI?

1 response

I am quite happy with the way it is.

Has Magic School AI helped you design more flexible, inclusive lessons aligned with UDL principles (e.g., offering multiple means of engagement, representation, or expression)? Please give an example.

1 response

These activities will help young children explore and understand the properties of different materials and how they are used in a fun and engaging way!

Exploring Properties of Materials

Objective: Students will be able to identify and describe the properties of different materials (glass, wood, fabric, metal, clay and plastic) and explain how these properties determine their uses.

Assessment:

Students will participate in a materials scavenger hunt, where they will find objects made from glass, wood, fabric, metal, and plastic around the classroom. They will then categorize these objects based on their material properties and share their findings with the class.

Key Points:

Properties of Materials: Discuss characteristics such as hardness, flexibility, transparency, and texture.

Different Materials: Identify and describe glass, wood, fabric, metal, and plastic.

Uses of Materials: Explain how the properties influence the uses of each material (e.g., glass is used for windows because it is transparent).

Categorization: Understand how to group objects based on similar material properties.

How do you feel Magic School AI supports your ability to balance technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge

1 response

Magic School AI significantly enhances my ability to balance technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge in a way that aligns perfectly with the developmental needs, learning profiles, and PYP philosophy reflected in the detailed observations and progress of our Early Years students.

Have you ever experienced a conflict between the convenience of AI (e.g., time-saving) and its alignment with your values, tone, or student needs? If yes, how did you navigate it?

1 response

No

Do you feel there's a trade-off between planning speed (efficiency) and the depth or personalisation of your lesson plans?

1 response

Do you feel there's a trade-off between planning speed (efficiency) and the depth or personalisation of your lesson plans? Please explain your choice

1 response

I use it to enhance my planning, I am check everything thoroughly. I never only use Magic School AI. I always personalise my planning.

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